

THE FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF GLASS FIBRE/EPOXY MATRIX FILAMENT WOUND PIPES

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue performance of GRE pipes under cyclic internal pressure has been investigated. The failure mode is weepage, a convoluted connected path of through thickness matrix cracks and ply delaminations. Fibres remain intact. By assuming that failure is controlled by matrix crack propagation, the use of fracture mechanics allows fatigue results for various fatigue cycles (both mean and amplitude variations) to be collapsed onto a single scaled stress against cycles to failure curve. This curve along with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is used to predict failure envelopes for GRE pipes under both internal pressure and axial load cyclic variations.

Keywords: crack propagation, Epoxy matrix, fatigue, Glass fibre, filament wound pipe, GRE, GRP

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in structural and semi-structural applications is becoming more widespread throughout the oil industry. As applications become more common and varied, the need to define and understand in engineering terms, the static and dynamic performance of composites becomes increasingly important. This paper is concerned with the fatigue performance of Glass fibre/Epoxy matrix (GRE) filament wound pipes and the development of a design procedure.

According to API Spec 15 HR the fatigue performance of GRE pipes may be determined by one or both of, two procedures, ASTM D-2992 procedure A for fully cyclic internal pressures, ASTM D-2992 procedure B for static pressures. Therefore pipes are specified and tested under either constant or fully cyclic internal pressures, neither loading case representative of typical operating conditions. Therefore a study into the effect of cyclic pressure loadings, both amplitude and mean pressure variations, on the lifetime of GRE high pressure linepipes was initiated. From this measured data and other data collated from manufacturers and open literature publications, a design procedure for predicting the lifetime of GRE pipes is proposed.

2. TEST RESULTS

2.1 Experimental Equipment

All pressure tests were performed using a multi-purpose servo-hydraulic testing machine capable of simultaneously applying axial tensile or compressive, torsional and bending loads. Static and dynamic internal pressures within the pipe, using water as the pressurising medium, were applied

using a separate pressurising unit consisting of an air driven pump in combination with electrically actuated valves. The resulting pressure waveform was approximately saw tooth with a maximum frequency of 0.15 Hz. This frequency was based on using 3 meter long pipes as test samples. For internal pressure tests, the external axial load on the (closed) pipe-ends was maintained at zero to obtain true free-end conditions. Each pipe was instrumented with strain gauges for axial and hoop strain measurement and a leak-detection wire was wrapped around the pipe to monitor pipe leakage. The pipes tested were standard 3 inch internal diameter GRE linepipes, with winding angles +/- 55 degrees with API 8 round threaded end connections.

2.2 Static Results

A set of static experiments, an axial tensile, a hoop and an internal pressure test were performed to determine the engineering moduli.

For the axial tensile test the pipe was loaded to 30kN. The response in both axial and hoop directions was linear elastic. At 10 kN the axial and hoop strain was 500 and -198 microstrain respectively corresponding to an axial Young's modulus of 14.9 GPa and an axial/hoop (load direction-axial, response direction-hoop) Poisson ratio of 0.39.

For the hoop test the pipe was pressurised to 25 bar with a corresponding axial compression load compensating for the induced axial end loads to produce a uni-directional hoop load. For a compressive load of 9.4 kN (zero axial stress), the hoop strain is 700 microstrain, corresponding to a hoop modulus of 20.0 GPa and hoop/axial (load direction-hoop, response direction-axial) Poisson ratio of 0.52.

Figure 1. Axial and hoop strain against internal pressure static test.

Figure 1 shows the axial and hoop strain for the internal pressure test up to 400 bar. The axial strain drops to -0.12% at 400 bar after a maximum of 0.05% at 160 bar. The hoop strain is significantly non-linear after a pressure of 180 bar, increasing rapidly to balance the rapidly decreasing axial strain. The limit of linear elastic behaviour, defined as the Ultimate Elastic Wall Stress (UEWS), is 110 bar corresponding to a hoop stress of 62 MPa. No weepage was observed during the test. A summary of the static mechanical properties of the pipe is listed in Table 1.

Table 1 - Mechanical properties of Smith Fiberglass 2000 psi 3 inch linepipe

	Manf.	Test I	Test II
E_{ax} (GPa)	11.4	14.9	13.9
E_{ho} (GPa)	31.1	20.0	20.3
Poisson's ratio (ax/ho)	0.11	0.39	0.38
Poisson's ratio (ho/ax)	0.4	0.52	0.55
UEWS (hoop Mpa/bar)		62/110	62/110

2.3 Fatigue Results

In total 5 cyclic pressure tests were performed; three tests with a mean pressure of 200 bar and amplitude levels 100-300, 125-275 and 150-250 bar, two tests with a mean pressure of 150 bar and amplitude levels 50-250 and 100-200 bar. All tests were stopped when leakage of the pipe was monitored by means of the detection tape installed around the pipe.

Data for the 125-275 bar fatigue test is presented in detail. Results from the other tests are similar in nature and the conclusions drawn from this test are applicable to the other tests. A summary of the test results is listed in Table 2.

Table 2 - Results of fatigue cycling of 3" linepipes

	150-250 bar	125-275 bar	100-300 bar	50-250 bar	100-200 bar
Cycles to failure	44400	32200	5500	12260	430200
Time to failure (hrs)	206	66	16.4	29.4	944
Average frequency (Hz)	0.06	0.13	0.09	0.12	0.13

Figure 2. Axial strain against internal pressure for fatigue test 125-275 bar.

For the 125-275 bar fatigue test, the pipe failed through weepage after 32200 cycles (65.8 hrs), a

practically uniform seepage of water along the pipe length. Figure 2 presents axial strain against internal pressure for the first and last few pressure cycles. A significant decrease in length (negative axial strain) of the pipe occurs. This is shown more clearly in Figure 3, which presents axial strain at 200 bar mean pressure against number of cycles. Also plotted in Figure 3 are axial strain results from the other 2 fatigue tests at 200 bar mean pressure.

Figure 3. Axial strain against number of cycles for fatigue tests 100-300 bar, 125-275 bar, 150-250 bar.

Figure 4. Microstructure of failure from fatigue test 125-275 bar.

Figure 4 presents a microstructure photograph of the failed pipe. Fibres are intact with ply

delaminations and through thickness matrix cracks resulting from the combination of matrix cracking and interfacial debonding. Weepage results from these through thickness cracks within each ply, linking together with delaminations, to form a convoluted path through the pipe wall.

After cycling, the pipes were subjected to an axial tensile and a hoop static test to measure the effect of matrix damage on the axial and hoop engineering moduli. For the axial tensile test, the pipe responded non-linear elastically, with an axial Young's modulus of 12.2 GPa, a decrease of 19% and an axial/hoop Poisson's ratio of 0.46, an increase of 18%. For the hoop test, the pipe responded almost linear elastically, with a hoop modulus of 14.9 GPa, a 29% decrease, and a hoop/axial Poisson's ratio of 0.56, a small decrease.

2.4 Discussion of static and fatigue test results

The engineering properties measured in the axial tensile and hoop static tests were repeatable. The axial modulus, on comparison with quoted manufacturer's values is in agreement, Table 1. However, the hoop modulus is 35% lower, the hoop/axial Poisson's ratio, 250% higher and the axial/hoop Poisson's ratio, 34% higher than quoted.

For the internal pressure static tests, the response of both axial and hoop strains is non-linear. The axial strain is non-linear after 65 bar while the hoop strain is significantly non-linear above 110 bar, defined as the UEWS, Table 2. This is less than the light duty rating, 138 bar (2000 psi), of the pipe but greater than the severe cyclic pressure duty rating, 104 bar (1500 psi). This non-linear behaviour results from the fact that the pipe is built up of +/- 55 degree plies, the optimum lay-up for the load carrying capacity of the pipe. However the load carrying capacity of each ply is not optimised and a significant in-plane shear stress carried by the matrix exists. The principal stress direction for GRE plies is +/- 67 degrees. Therefore, if plies were free to rotate, they would tend to align towards the +/- 67 degree direction, this rotation being driven by the in-plane shearing forces. Initially, plies are restrained from movement, but during testing ply delamination occurs permitting some ply rotation. This rotation causes the decrease in axial strain.

For the fatigue tests the axial strain behaviour is as explained, despite the change from static to cyclic loading. Cycling will enhance delamination growth permitting rotation of the plies towards +/- 67 degrees.

3. A DESIGN PROCEDURE FOR GRE PIPELINES

The current design procedure for GRE high pressure line-pipe is based on API Specification 15 HR. This specification consists of two sub-procedures for determining the long term hydrostatic and working pressures under constant or fully cyclic internal pressure. The operating or working pressure for either static or cyclic duty is calculated from the long term hydrostatic pressure (LTHP) determined from the respective sub-procedure, times a factor of safety, typically 0.5. A drawback of the current design specification is that both sub-procedures represent the extremes of normal operating conditions. Typically average working conditions would be a prescribed mean pressure with superimposed pressure fluctuations, typically of lower magnitude than the mean.

Figure 5 presents typical static and fully cyclic pressure data supplied by a manufacturer. The data is generally presented as the logarithm of hoop stress (or maximum internal pressure) against the logarithm of time. For cyclic data this time is an equivalent time, based on a testing frequency of 25 cycles per minute. Regression lines are drawn through the data points for both procedures and are of the form;

$$\text{Log(Hoop stress or Pressure)} = A - B \text{Log(Equivalent time)} \quad (1)$$

Figure 5. Typical static and cyclic regression curves for GRE linepipe.

The LTHP is defined for a lifetime of 20 years. For fully cyclic conditions this time corresponds to 262.8 million cycles.

If operating conditions are not static or fully cyclic then, the ASTM specification recommends that the fully cyclic curve should be used, if cyclic data is available, to determine the LTHP(cy). If only static data is available, then the LTHP(st) is multiplied by an extra service factor to account for pressure cycling. This service factor is 0.25, because experience has shown that the LTHP(st) is never greater than a factor of 4 times the LTHP(cy).

What is required is a simple yet rigorous procedure/guide-line for determining the LTHP and working pressure which accounts for both the mean and amplitude of the pressure cycle. Microstructural results show that the failure of GRE pipes under various pressure cycle conditions is through thickness matrix cracking and ply delamination with intact fibres. Therefore, failure is controlled by cracks propagating within the matrix. Williams (ref.1) has shown that fatigue crack growth within epoxy resin is controlled by the local high stresses around the crack tip plus a constant growth factor per fatigue cycle, a function of the ratio of minimum to maximum pressure, R , and that the effective stress intensity factor is;

$$K_{eff} = K (1 - R^2) \quad (2)$$

where K = far field stress intensity factor ($Nmm^{3/2}$)

R = minimum pressure/maximum pressure

Also, it was shown that the matrix crack growth due to fatigue follows a Paris law;

$$da/dN = A (K_{eff})^m \quad (3)$$

where a = crack length (mm)

N = number of cycles

A = proportionality constant

m = experimentally determined exponent, typically between 6 and 10 for Epoxy resin

Since the far field stress intensity factor, K , is proportional to the applied stress, then crack growth

is proportional to the factor, $(1 - R^2)$ times the applied stress. Therefore, when presenting GRE pipe fatigue data, stress (or pressure) against cycles to failure, where the failure mode results from matrix crack propagation, then the hoop stress should be scaled accordingly;

$$\text{Scaled stress} = (1 - R^2) * \text{Max.Hoop stress}^2 \quad (4)$$

Figure 6. Comparison between manufacturers' GRE fatigue data and experimentally measured data produced by Shell and Battelle using new scaled variable.

Figure 6 presents scaled hoop stress against the logarithm of cycles to failure for various fatigue tests with various R values. The fatigue data comes from manufacturers' and Battelle (ref.2) and collapses onto a single curve within experimental error. Also the measured data points, for cycles from 5,000 to 450,000, collapse onto the same single curve, indicating that the newly defined scaling variable provides a rigorous means for presenting GRE fatigue data. Plotted also in Figure 6 is a line representing a fully cyclic fatigue curve using the measured UEWS as the maximum hoop stress. The fatigue results appear to tend to a fatigue limit, approximately equal to the UEWS fatigue curve. The other curve plotted in Figure 6 is the integral of Equation (3), using an exponent of 8, with a suitably chosen constant of integration. The agreement between this curve and the experimental data points is reasonable providing further evidence that matrix crack propagation is the controlling mechanism for GRE pipe fatigue failure.

To predict GRE pipe failure under combined internal pressure plus axial loads, the results of Figure 6 along with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion are used. The failure criterion (ref.3) is;

$$F_{ij} s_i s_j + F_i s_i = k \quad (i,j = 1,2,6) \quad (5)$$

where F_{ij} , F_i = strength constants (m^4/MPa^2 , m^2/MPa) s_i = stress, i th direction (MPa/m^2)

The normalised interaction strength constant, F_{12} , is taken as -0.5, (ref.3). The physical interpretation of k is the allowable safety factor. Reducing the safety factor, k , (i.e. the size of the failure envelope) provides a method for introducing reductions in pipe strength due to fatigue loadings. A regression curve, RC, fitted to the data in Figure 6, normalised to unity at zero cycles is given by;

$$RC = 1 - 0.1242 \log(N) - 0.04754 \log(N)^2 + 0.0109 \log(N)^3 - 0.00061 \log(N)^4 \quad (6)$$

Equating RC to k^2 provides the failure envelope for a given number of cycles. Figure 7 presents

failure envelopes, maximum hoop against axial stress, for GRE linepipe for 100 to 1,000,000 cycles with $R=0$ for both hoop and axial cyclic stresses. Different R values for the hoop and axial directions can be included by appropriate scaling within the Tsai-Wu failure criterion to obtain an overall value for k . No experimental verification of Figure 7 is available, however work is continuing to provide such verification.

Figure 7. Failure envelopes with fatigue correlations for GRE linepipe.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A comparison between manufacturers' quoted results and static test measurements revealed that for the specific GRE pipe tested, only the axial Young's modulus was in agreement, within 10%. The difference is significantly greater for the other engineering moduli. The UEWS, or limit of linear elasticity, is less than the low duty rating, 138 bar, but greater than the severe duty rating, 104 bar. Since these tests the data from manufacturers' have become closer to the values measured.

Microstructural investigations showed that the fatigue failure mode of GRE pipes is weepage, a convoluted path of connected through thickness matrix cracks and ply delaminations. Fibres remain intact.

A new scaling procedure for plotting GRE fatigue data is proposed on the assumption that matrix crack propagation controls failure. Using this scaled variable fatigue data are reduced onto a single curve. Further this variable is used, along with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion to predict failure envelopes for GRE pipes under combined internal pressure cycling and axial loads. The result is a design pressure for a given number of cycles based on the actual loading conditions.

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